

Retarded Time and Radiation from an Accelerated Charge Part III

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In Newtonian mechanics, -grad of a potential is associated with force as is the second derivative of time acting on a position vector r . In the case of a moving charge, the notion of retarded potential is used, where the time at a measurement point is not the time associated with a source point which sends a signal (travelling at the speed of light in a vacuum c). In fact, the time of the source point (corresponding to t at the measurement point) is $t - R/c$ where $R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|$, \mathbf{r} vector being from a fixed origin to the measurement point and \mathbf{r}' vector from the fixed origin to a piece of charge. As a result, the r variable appears as a spatial variable in potentials, but also in the time variable position. As a result, -grad which usually acts strictly on spatial variables has the possibility of acting on a time variable.

If E (electric field) has the sense of force (through - grad ϕ and other terms), then having grad $\rightarrow d/dt$ partial with a charge density which already contains a d/dt partial would yield $d/dt d/dt$ partial which is like $d/dt dr/dt = \text{acceleration}$ for a Newtonian accelerating object, quite different from the usual - grad ϕ . Grad $\rightarrow d/dt$, but a Taylor expansion of a source, such as charge density, using retarded time also brings in a d/dt partial, so in fact there are two $d/dt d/dt$ partials meaning that the term -grad ϕ does not just represent a piece of electric field force, but also a piece of acceleration type force if a charge is accelerating (i.e. $d/dt d/dt$ partial does not return 0). In other words, retarded time places a moving particle into the field picture (because signals leave charge pieces at retarded times) and so derivatives necessarily act on this motion in the field (which has its own interpretation apart from the usual electric field causing an r in the denominator of expressions to increase by 1.). In other words, retarded time leads to a mixture of -grad potential pieced linked with the electrostatic potential and Newtonian mechanics acting on $d/dt d/dt$ partial r . The Newtonian accelerating object is no longer coupled to the charge system and may move off freely, hence radiated photons from an accelerating charge.

Newtonian Mechanics

In Newtonian mechanics (second law)

$$dp/dt = \text{Force} \quad ((1a)) \rightarrow m d/dt dr \text{ vector}/dt = \text{Force vector} \quad ((1b))$$

if $m = \text{constant}$ (nonrelativistic form)

If one considers a point charge and ignores the tiny mass linked with the electromagnetic fields, one might consider this as a Newtonian object which accelerates like any other Newtonian object. In this approximation, one ignores the electric/magnetic fields of the particle and simply considers it to be a moving/accelerating Newtonian object.

Electromagnetism

On the other hand, one may wish to know the details of changes in the electric and magnetic fields of a moving charged particle. The question is: How does one find such information? Maxwell's electromagnetic equations describe the electric E and magnetic B fields associated with charge densities and moving charge densities so it seems they may be used to solve for E and B to show the effects of the motion/acceleration of the core charges.

In other words, there seems to be a separation of physics. As a starting point, the charge density moves at a velocity v and may have an acceleration dv/dt without any consideration of electric/magnetic fields. The velocity and acceleration appear as constraints imposed on the electromagnetic system. Separate electromagnetic results appear as a consequence of imposing the constraints of v and dv/dt on Maxwell's em equations.

The problem with the above description is that it does not account for the Newtonian particle effects introduced through the notion of retarded time. Retarded time is defined in the following manner. Imagine one wishes to measure E or B at a point r vector (measured from a fixed origin) at time t . Second, imagine that each piece of charge density sends a signal traveling at the speed of light in a vacuum, c , to the measurement point. If each signal is to arrive at the same time t , the signals must leave at different times dependent of r' vector which is measured from the fixed origin to the measurement point:

t (time) in charge density is replaced with $t - R/c$ where $R = |r \text{ vector} - r' \text{ vector}|$ ((2))

After this substitution in charge and current density, one might feel that the result may be left to the mathematics in Maxwell's em equations, but we suggest that the introduction of retarded time places the notion of a Newtonian particle into the electric fields.

This is due to two effects. The first is a Taylor expansion of a charge density(r' vector, $t-R/c$) which brings in one d/dt partial. The second is due to $-\text{grad} \rightarrow 1/c d/dt$ partial when acting on $t-R/c$ (expanded).

Newtonian Particle Consequences of Retarded Time

Retarded time means that the usual time variable is now a function of r vector. This implies that a derivative with respect to r acts on a time variable and so by the chain rule one has:

$d/dr \rightarrow \text{speed } d/dt \text{ partial}$ ((3))

In particular, a $-\text{grad}$ which usually yields force in Newtonian mechanics through $\text{Force} = -\text{grad } V$, now yields $d/dt \text{ partial } V(x)$. If $V(x)$ were to already contain a d/dt partial piece, one would have $d/dt d/dt \text{ partial}$, which is the form of Newtonian acceleration of a particle. The immediate question is: How would a potential already contain d/dt partial? We suggest that if the potential depends on sources at r' vector at t , then replacing t with retarded time and doing an expansion using (1)

$R = |r \text{ vector} - r' \text{ vector}| \text{ approx} = r - r' \text{ vector} \cdot r \text{ vector} / r$ ((3))

Then $\text{function}(\mathbf{r}', t - R/c) = \text{function}(\mathbf{r}', t - r/c + \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / cr)$

Approx = $\text{function}(\mathbf{r}', t-r/c) + \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / (cr) \frac{d \text{function}}{dt}$ partial at \mathbf{r}' vector and $t-r/c$ ((4))

Thus, it is possible to have d/dt appear in an approximate expression for the source of a force and then have a second d/dt enter through $-\text{grad}$ becoming $1/c \frac{d}{dt}$ partial.

This acceleration is physically very different from $-\text{grad } \phi$ which tests the changes due to changing r (which often drops as $1/r$ (power).).

In other words, the notion of $-\text{grad } V$ due to a dropping off of V with r is mixed with a Newtonian particle accelerating with no notion of checking the dropping rate of V with r . Two decoupled systems coexist, but the Newtonian accelerating object is not held by the charge system and may actually move off (i.e. decouple itself altogether). We apply these ideas to an accelerating charged particle.

Accelerating Charged Particle

Maxwell's electromagnetic equations lead mathematically to the definitions of a scalar electrostatic potential ϕ and a magnetic vector potential A such that:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial} \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad B = \text{grad} \times A \quad ((5b))$$

Furthermore, $\frac{1}{2} \epsilon_0 E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} \mu_0 B \cdot B$ is considered to be energy density and $c^{-1} E \times B$, momentum density. (This also follows from Maxwell's equations.)

Here, we only consider $-\text{grad } \phi$ because it is of the same form as $-\text{grad}$ potential in Newtonian mechanics. $Q_1 E$ yields force due to the electric field (Q_1 is a test charge) and $-\text{grad } \phi$ is one piece of this force as seen in ((5a)).

The electrostatic potential may be written in terms of a source charge density evaluated at a retarded time, i.e.:

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \int \frac{\text{charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t-R/c) dV'}{R} \quad ((6a))$$

In (1) explicit equations are calculated for ϕ , A , E and B . Here, we simply wish to show the Newtonian object embedded in the electric field due to the introduction of retarded time and so we do not display full values of ϕ , A , E and B .

The key point is the expansion of $\text{charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t-R/c) =$

$$\text{Charge density}(\mathbf{r}', t-r/c + \mathbf{r}' \cdot \mathbf{r} / (cr)) =$$

Charge density(ρ' vector, $t-r/c$) + ρ' vector dot \mathbf{r} vector/(cr) d/dt partial charge density (at \mathbf{r}' vector and $t-r/c$) ((7))

For large \mathbf{r} vector compared with \mathbf{r}' vector one may see that $1/R$ goes as $1/r$ as the leading term. Thus, the integral of $d\mathbf{v}'$ acting on the d/dt piece in ((7)) yields:

\mathbf{r} vector dot $d\mathbf{p}/dt$ where \mathbf{p} is the dipole moment, i.e. $\mathbf{p}=q \mathbf{r}'$ vector for point charge ((8))

One must remember, however, that the dipole moment is evaluated at the retarded time $t-r/c$. Thus, $d\mathbf{p}/dt$ partial = $q\mathbf{v}$ at $t-r/c$.

In Newtonian mechanics, $-\text{grad } \phi$ is used to determine the force due to the change in a potential in r . Often, the potential drops in r as in the case of a nonmoving point charge for which $\phi=q/r$.

One sees that the d/dt partial acting on the dipole moment brings in \mathbf{v} , i.e. one already has a moving Newtonian object. Usually, $-\text{grad}$ would not affect such a term, but with the presence of the retarded time $t-r/c$, $-\text{grad}$ leads to $d/dr \rightarrow 1/c d/dt$ partial. In other words, one obtains:

d/dt partial $p(t-r/c) = 1/c dp/dt = 1/c dv/dt = 1/c$ acceleration ((9))

Thus, an accelerating Newtonian object is embedded in the electric field because ((9)) follows from $-\text{grad } \phi$ which is part of \mathbf{E} where $q_1 \mathbf{E}$ is the electric force acting on a test charge q_1 . One may note that acceleration is also proportional to force for a Newtonian object, although one does not have a rest mass in this case.

As a result, $-\text{grad } \phi$ acts on $1/r$ and other $1/\{r(\text{power})\}$ terms, leading to \mathbf{E} pieces which drop off in r rapidly and represent the usual $-\text{grad}$ potential force, but embedded in this scenario is an accelerating Newtonian object which does not drop off as $1/(rr)$ or faster. (This is a direct consequence of retarded time which gives each piece of charge its own identity or degree of freedom so to speak because it sends a signal at its own time linked to \mathbf{r}' vector.)

This Newtonian object is decoupled from the \mathbf{E} field bound to the charges and represents an object which may move off on its own, so to speak. This, we argue, is the radiation which is emitted from an accelerating charge and is due to the introduction of a Newtonian object through retarded time which links spatial derivatives to time ones.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the use of retarded time, i.e. the mixing of time and space in what is usually a strictly time variable, through $t \rightarrow t - R/c$ where $R=|\mathbf{r}$ vector - \mathbf{r}' vector| leads to a spatial derivative becoming linked with a time derivatives through the chain rule. Here, \mathbf{r} vector is taken from a fixed origin to a measurement point at time t , and \mathbf{r}' vector from the same origin to a charge density piece.

In Newtonian mechanics, $-\text{grad } \phi$ is usually taken to be force, and Maxwell's equations are consistent with this (but more complicated). One may note that the electric force on a test charge q_1 is $F = q_1 E$ and $E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt}$ partial. Thus, the usual $-\text{grad } \phi$ Newtonian force piece is present, but augmented by $-\frac{dA}{dt}$ partial. In Newtonian mechanics, the force due to $-\text{grad } \phi$ usually measures changes due to a dropping r in ϕ , e.g. $1/(rr)$ etc. If retarded time is present, however, $d/dr \rightarrow d/dt$ partial, in other words one measures time changes as in those due to a moving Newtonian object. This is completely different than the dropping off of r . Newtonian force, however, is linked to d/dt d/dt , not a single d/dt . One may note that if one expands a charge source with retarded time, i.e. Charge density (r' vector, $t-R/c$), then a d/dt partial appears in this expansion. This d/dt is then acted on by d/dt partial from $-\text{grad}$ because the resulting function still contains the retarded time. As a result, one has a fully accelerating Newtonian object embedded in the electric field. This object is not bound to the charge distribution, but is free and may move off. We suggest that this is an idea behind radiating photons from an accelerating charge.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory (Addison-Wesley 1980)